

Tension and the Cello

Sheanna Wirasinghe

For the original, full version of this publication, visit:

(<https://timbreandorchestration.org/writings/amazing-moments-in-timbre/2023/4/26/tension-and-the-cello>)

Abstract

Kaija Saariaho's *Petals*, 1988, transforms the cello into a diverse tool capable of creating countless varying sounds. Her organization of sounds produces two distinct timbral profiles that alter throughout the work, governing its two-part structure. Different music variables, including temporal perception, sound characteristics, density, and attack, are employed by each profile to construct several binaries that either produce a state of tension or relaxation. The superimposition of profiles towards the end of *Petals* begets the work's climax by maximizing tension. Saariaho therefore develops a narrative that explores opposing approaches to the creation and dissolution of tension through timbre.

Keywords

Timbre, Form, Tension, Binaries, Kaija Saariaho, *Petals*, *Nymphéa*

Introduction

Like the shattering of a glass, Kaija Saariaho fragments a single instrument into countless distinct timbres, allowing her to construct a dichotomous musical narrative. Composed in 1988, *Petals* is a solo cello work (with optional amplification and signal processing) derived from musical ideas originally presented in her string quartet *Nymphéa* (1987). *Nymphéa* translates to "Water Lily," therefore making *Petals* a felicitous title considering the work's solo instrumentation, condensed structure, and reduced length.

Although the cello itself can be classified within its own timbral profile (Reymore, 2022), Saariaho utilizes extended techniques to produce an extensive variety of sounds. Her use of the *Estremamente Flautando* (EF) marking, for example, transforms the cello into what sounds like a high-pitched flute, heard in audio example 1 (<https://tinyurl.com/yjhabetp>). Saariaho's organization of these sounds produces a binary of two contrasting timbral profiles that form the basis for the work's two-part structure. Each timbral profile relies on a set of musical parameters to produce a state of tension that governs the work's narrative. Tension is maximized when both timbral profiles overlap in the climax, displaying the work's multifaceted approach to tension using a diverse timbral palette.

Binaries

A sonic dichotomy manifests throughout this work. According to Saariaho's program notes:

“The opposite elements here are fragile coloristic passages which give birth to more energetic events with clear rhythmic and melodic character... In bringing together these very opposite modes of expressions I aimed to force the interpreter to stretch his sensibility” (Saariaho, n.d).

Petals therefore unfolds as an alteration between two sound worlds, consisting of contrasting passages I label as either belonging to timbral profile 1 (TP1) or 2 (TP2). The first timbral profile is exemplified through the beginning of the work, from 0:00 – 1:00 (audio example 2: <https://tinyurl.com/3zrz5j>). These passages are always marked *lento* and express a smooth and subdued character. The passages that characterize TP2, exemplified through 1:00 – 1:24 (audio example 3: <https://tinyurl.com/3fbsj3uc>), are faster, louder, and rhythmically driven with clear, pulsing notes and microtonal inflections. Shown in figure 1, spectrograms of the two passage types demonstrate their contrasting sound worlds. The *lento*, TP1 in figure 1a comprises horizontal, blurry lines mainly concentrated in the lower frequency range (~5000Hz and under). By contrast, figure 1b models TP2; the sharper, vertical lines are comparably more intense in color and have a broader frequency range.

Figure 1. Spectrograms of the two timbral profiles in Petals

The opposing extremes presented in figure 1 alternate throughout the piece, producing a back-and-forth dialogue that creates an ABABABA form (see table 1), whereby A represents TP1 and B represents TP2. This structural narrative aligns with the altering pattern between relative (always *lento*) and precise tempo markings. The resulting constant timbral binary contributes to a multifaceted state of tension, as described below.

Form	Tempo	Profile	Timestamp
A ₁	<i>Lento</i>	TP1	0:00 – 1:00
B ₁	♩ = 60	TP2	1:00 – 1:24
A ₂	<i>Lento</i>	TP1	1:24 – 2:14
B ₂	♩ = 54	TP2	2:14 – 2:55
A ₃	<i>Lento</i>	TP1	2:55 – 4:33
B ₃	♩ = 60	TP2?	4:33 – 6:37
A ₄	<i>Lento</i>	TP1	6:37 – 8:24

Table 1. Form of Petals

Tension

Tension in music is a complex concept lacking an exact, unanimous definition. It has been informally described as a feeling of rising intensity or climax, whereas a decrease in tension corresponds to a feeling of relaxation or resolution (Farbood, 2012). Regarding a sense of expectation, Roni Y. Granot and Zohar Eitan (2011) list musical events considered as unstable or incomplete as promoters of tension and events considered stable and complete as indicators of relaxation. They furthermore recognize tension as encompassing an increase in intensity through levels of musical activity. Tension can therefore be regarded in an inverse relationship with relaxation, caused by a sense of anticipation or disequilibrium. Musical variables, such as temporal perception (sense of tempo), sound characteristics, spectral density, and a sound's attack, produce suspense, destabilize a music segment, and populate the sonic space. Attack refers to the onset of a sound and spectral density relates to how much space the sound or sounds take up. The former concerns the spectral-temporal features of the beginning portion of a given

sound, while the latter concerns its spectral distribution and bandwidth (this is depicted in a spectrogram by the area of red—see below). The binaries within the musical variables, detailed in table 2, function to create a balanced duality by using the same variable categories to create or remove a state of tension. While the two timbral profiles are not mutually exclusive, they identify themselves by predominantly including characteristics belonging to one profile.

Variable	TP1		TP2	
Temporal Perception	Stasis; slow/no sense of time Longer note values Gradual/steady dynamics	Relaxation	Directionality; rhythmically dense, fast pulse Short note values Swift dynamic changes	Tension
Sound Characteristics	'Noisy' sounds Indiscernible motifs	Tension	'Clean' sounds Stronger sense of musical motifs	Relaxation
	Softer dynamics	Relaxation	Louder dynamics	Tension
Density	Timbrally dense	Tension	Timbrally sparse	Relaxation
Attack	Softer attacks; mild	Relaxation	Harsher attacks; more intense	Tension

Table 2. Binaries present in the two timbral profiles

Passages in TP1 generally create tension using noisier, obscure sounds that contribute to a denser timbral profile, indicative by the blurry red lines and unclear gaps in figure 1a. In opposition, passages belonging to TP2 have clearer sound characteristics that are sparser in texture and relax tension. TP2 builds tension using extensive dynamics and short note values that simulate a higher perceived tempo and create harsher attacks. TP1 maintains a steadier sense of time and softer attacks to relax tension. Table 3 depicts the various mechanisms observed in the A and B sections that support a musical variable belonging to either TP1 or TP2.

Characteristics of A (TP1)	Variables	Characteristics of B (TP2)	Variables
Bow Pressure 	Sound Characteristics		
Glissando 	Temporal Perception Sound Characteristics Attack		
Tremolo Drone notes	Sound Characteristics Temporal Perception	Stronger sense of musical motifs Conjunct lines	Sound Characteristics
Ritardando	Temporal Perception	Accelerando	Temporal Perception

Table 3. Sound shapes and articulations in TP1 and TP2

Figure 3. Spectrogram of section B3; 4:33 – 6:37

Many TP2 characteristics, including accents, pizzicato markings, and ascending figures are juxtaposed with TP1 attributes such as glissandi, tremolos, and long drone notes. The sharp 16th and 32nd note-attacks convey a distressed feeling, further magnified with ascending figures producing a sense of expectation and instability. While the ritardando marking and quieter dynamics exemplify a method of releasing tension by promoting stasis, it is repeatedly interrupted by a return of tempo and TP2 characteristics, maximizing tension between the two profiles.

Specific TP1 characteristics have a shifting role that brings the first timbral profile to the forefront. Bow pressure, for example, is frequently added throughout this passage, thereby transforming the timbres heard by adding overtones and crowding the musical space, obscuring the pitched sound. The scratchy sound resulting gives an impression of increased timbral activity by saturating the music space with noise. This TP1 technique of creating tension is initially played during the second half of the motive (the long note value section) but is slowly added to the beginning of the motive as the passage progresses. The third and fourth arrows outline two of five instances where bow pressure is added in this manner, the intense red shade illustrating an increase in timbral density during moments of high rhythmic activity. As the bow pressure markings become superimposed on the ascending figures and accented notes, Saariaho maximizes tension by combining the two timbral profiles. From 6:13 to the end of B3, most of the articulations belong to TP1 musical variables used to decrease tension, signaling the end of the piece, and leading into the final section.

Overall, *Petals* highlights Saariaho's innovative compositional process in manipulating material derived from cello sounds to create a timbrally diverse and sonically rich work. She utilizes timbre as a structuring principle to enrich the composition with numerous polarities, creating an effective musical narrative that showcases the diversity of the cello.

Video Link: <https://youtu.be/DOMON-OnfBA>

Works Cited

Farbood, M. M. (2012). A Parametric, Temporal Model of Musical Tension. *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 29(4), 387–428. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2012.29.4.387>

Granot, R. Y., & Eitan, Z. (2011). Musical Tension and the Interaction of Dynamic Auditory Parameters. *Music Perception: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, 28(3), 219–246. <https://doi.org/10.1525/mp.2011.28.3.219>

Reymore, L. (2022). Characterizing prototypical musical instrument timbres with timbre trait profiles. *Musicae Scientiae*, 26(3), 648–674. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10298649211001523>

Saariaho, K. (n.d.). *Petals*. *Petals* " Kaija Saariaho. Retrieved April 21, 2022, from <https://saariaho.org/works/petals/>